

Treatment of Enteroatmospheric Fistula with Rivera'S Condom Technique: Case Report and Literature Review

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ABSTRACT

The management of enteroatmospheric fistulas is a complex challenge for the surgeon, requiring strategic planning and nutritional support for favorable healing. We present the use of the Rivera condom technique for isolating enteroatmospheric fistulas.

KEYWORDS: Enteroatmospheric fistula, Rivera's condom technique, Open abdomen.

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INTRODUCTION

Enteroatmospheric fistula (EAF) is defined as a type of enterocutaneous fistula which, surrounded by granulation tissue or exposed viscera, discharges its content on a laparostomic wound.(1)

An enteroatmospheric fistula (EAF) represents a catastrophic complication that often occurs in the setting of an open abdomen (OA) (2)

Complications of prolonged Open Abdomen (OA) are the development of adhesions, scarring, lateralization of the abdominal wall and finally frozen abdomen. This course of events predisposes also to the development of EAF, which have an incidence ranging from 5% to 35%¹ and a mortality rate of 20% to 44%.(1,3)

CASE PRESENTATION

We present the case of a 62-year-old male patient with a recently diagnosed of diabetes, hospitalized 15 years prior

due to intestinal obstruction that did not require surgical treatment, heavy smoking and alcoholism, and he discontinued at age 30.

His surgical history included exploratory laparotomy with intestinal resection and entero-entero anastomosis secondary to a strangulated right inguinal hernia with ileal perforation.

He was admitted to our hospital unit for a strangulated right inguinal hernia, for which he underwent exploratory laparotomy, requiring intestinal resection and end-to-end entero-entero anastomosis due to ileal perforation.

He subsequently underwent reoperation for anastomotic dehiscence with generalized peritonitis, for which an ileostomy was performed. The patient developed a surgical site infection and wound dehiscence, progressing to a Bjork 4 hostile abdomen with the development of an enteroatmospheric fistula.

Figure 1: Surgical wound dehiscence secondary to surgical site infection.

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Given the patient's severe malnutrition and limited resources in the unit, management was decided upon using the Rivera Condom technique to isolate the fistula. The patient progressed well until contamination and the infectious process were limited, as described in the following images.

Nutritional and antimicrobial treatment were initiated, along with scheduled Rivera Condom replacements and dressings. Due to the significant reduction in the wound size and a negative culture, the patient was discharged for outpatient management with dressings.

Figure 2: Fistula isolation using the Rivera condom placement technique (left image). Hydrocolloid paste placed to prevent leakage through the Rivera condom (right image).

Figure 3. Wound after 3 weeks of treatment with on-demand replacements of Rivera condoms and dressings with sodium hypochlorite solution.

Figure 4. Wound at 6 weeks treated on an outpatient basis with sodium hypochlorite solution dressings, with complete closure of the fistula.

Figure 5. Wound prior to closure, with culture report showing absence of bacterial development.

DISCUSSION

The level of complexity of enteroatmospheric fistulas varies depending on their anatomical location, whether they are low- or high-output fistulas, and the etiology of the fistula.

The cornerstone of enterocutaneous fistula treatment is adequate nutritional and infectious control. Currently, the use of supplemental nutrition has improved the outcome of patients with enteroatmospheric fistulas. However, it requires a long healing process that can last for months, posing a significant challenge for even the most experienced surgeons. (4)

Currently, there are various proposals and techniques for the treatment of enteroatmospheric fistulas, ranging from traditional techniques to advanced devices such as the application of negative pressure. However, the hospital setting and the patient's clinical context must be considered when deciding which therapeutic strategy to use. (5)

In our patient's case, since we were in a rural hospital with highly limited healthcare resources, we opted for a highly recognized traditional procedure, the Rivera condom placement technique. We obtained excellent results in fistula isolation. This allowed us to adequately control the surgical site infection, effectively treating the wound completely without the need for multiple surgical interventions. It also allowed for subsequent outpatient management, thus reducing care costs and the risk of further complications for the patient.

CONCLUSION

The use of traditional techniques for isolating enteroatmospheric fistulas is very useful for the process of closing enteroatmospheric fistulas as well as for controlling the associated infection.

CONFLICTS OF INTEREST

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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INFORMED CONSENT STATEMENT

Written informed consent was obtained from the patient for publication of this case report and accompanying images. A written copy is available upon request.

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